

Prospects of Metal Nitride Intermediate Layer for FRM

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ABSTRACT

An intermediate layer between a reinforcement and a matrix may be effective to prevent deterioration during fabrication or utilizing at a high temperature. Ti- or Cr nitride plating was performed by ion-plating method. Various compositions and orientations of nitrides were obtained by changing the plating conditions.

In the case of the TiN plated pyrolytic carbon substrate, reaction was hardly observed after heat treatment. On the other hand, in the case of the TiN plated stainless steel substrate, slight amount of Cr was observed at the surface of the TiN layer. The layer adhered tightly to both kinds of substrates. TiN is hopefully expected as an intermediate layer.

In the case of the Cr or its nitride plated pyrolytic carbon, carbide was formed after heat treatment. In the case of Cr₂N on stainless steel, Fe and Cr were found at the surface of the layer. CrN plated stainless steel was stable but honeycomb like cracks were found on the surface. CrN layer was rather easily separated from the substrates.

INTRODUCTION

FRM is expected as a heat resisting material. However, serious deterioration of the reinforcement by reaction with the matrix was often observed during fabrication and/or after holding at a high temperature for a long time (1-3). On the other hand, wettability is important for fabrication (4, 5). Therefore preventing the deterioration and improving wettability are hopefully expected for fabrication and utilizing the composite materials.

Methods against the problems are roughly classified as follows: 1) putting one or few kinds of intermediate layers between the reinforcement and the matrix (4, 5). 2) adding some alloying elements into the matrix (5). 3) changing the properties of the reinforcement (6).

Each method has merits and demerits. For example, methods in the category of No 2 have merits that preparation is easy and productivity is high. On the other hand, some elements, which can give remarkable effects for one composite material, cannot necessarily show fine effects on another composite.

The methods of No 3 are generally difficult for us as they should be done during fabrication of the reinforcement. Therefore we studied on the method of No 1 in this report.

The intermediate layer should basically have two properties, e.g. good wettability to the matrix metal and no reactivity on the reinforcement and also on the matrix metal. These properties are often incompatible with each other. Good affinity, for example, is preferable for the wettability, but, on the contrary, the affinity causes usually undesirable reaction between the plated intermediate layer and the matrix metal. If we prepare an metal intermediate layer on a reinforcement, it is usually good for the wettability to the matrix. However the metal layer is often, more or less, soluble into the matrix metal at high temperature. Such the layer is not suitable for the intermediate layer. On the other hand, it is well known that carbon does not react and/or dissolve in copper. Then if a carbon soot layer is put between a reinforcement and copper matrix, it may be difficult to fabricate a composite material because of its poor wettability. And even if it is fabricated, transferring stress from the matrix to the reinforcement must be awfully poor.

From such points of view, fine ceramics such as nitride are expected for a good intermediate layer. In this report, we studied on the compatibility between Ti, Cr or each nitride and carbon or stainless steel.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

SUS 304(18-8 stainless steel) and pyrolytic carbon were used for the substrates. The pyrolytic carbon was produced by decomposition of methane gas at 1800°C, and has approximately the same C_e value as one of high tensile strength carbon fibre which is usually used for reinforcement. Moreover the pyrolytic carbon has good preferred orientation of crystallite and has flat surface, which are desirable for observing the compatibility.

The surface of the stainless steel plate was mechanically polished, cleansed with soap, rinsed completely with running water and consequently dried in a vacuum at 120°C. The pyrolytic carbon was also mechanically polished at first, but was cleansed in trichloroethylene and dried as same way as the stainless steel plate.

99%Ti and 99.5%Cr were used for the metal source. Both of the metals were degassed in a vacuum before using.

5-nine Ar and 5-nine N₂ were used for plasma and forming nitrides, respectively.

A hollow cathode discharge (HCD) type ion-plating instrument was used for plating metal or metal nitride. The demention of its vacuum chamber is 600mm of inner diameter and 155 liter of the volume.

Several pieces of pyrolytic carbon and pieces of stainless steel plates were set on a stainless steel frame. The frame was set at the centre of the chamber, and the metal source was set in a water cooled copper crucible at the bottom of the chamber. The samples were heated at 400°C before starting plating.

Ar gas was introduced into the chamber to 4×10^{-5} Torr from the hollow cathode which was set between the substrate and the crucible, and 1kV was applied to let discharge for cleaning the surface of the substrate by ion bombardment. The bombardment cleaning was carried out for 20min.

The metal was evaporated by argon plasma with 20cc/min of Ar flow rate and 35volt x 300ampere of electric power. The plasma was focused to the metal source in the crucible by using a magnetic coil. As the metal vapour was ionized and activated by counter flow of Ar plasma to allow forming nitride and

promoting adhesion of the layer to the substrate. The plating was carried out under the conditions described above for 20min. The thickness of the obtained layer was about 20 μ m in the case of metal only and several μ m in the case of nitride.

Crystal structure of each plated layer was determined by X-ray diffraction profile comparing with ASTM cards. Cu-K α was used as the X-ray source for Ti and its nitrides, and Co-K α was for Cr and its nitrides.

The obtained samples were wrapped with Ti foil and heat treated at 1000°C for 75 hours in a vacuum of 10⁻⁶Torr. The foil was used to avoid contamination by residual oxygen.

The composition analysis was performed at the transverse section around the interface by EPMA. Before preparing the EPMA sample, protection coating was performed on the layer. The coating adheres tightly to the specimen and aid in eliminating edge rounding.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The morphology of the plated layers changed by changing the flow rate of N₂ in both cases of Ti- and Cr- groups. Ti layer without N₂ was almost smooth and compact but slight unevenness was observed. When N₂ was introduced and the flow rate of N₂ was increased, the surface showed more flaky appearance. Morphology of the Ti layer without N₂ and the layer from Ti with 250cc/min of N₂ are shown in Photos 1-a and -b, respectively. The layer from Ti with the flow rate between 0 and 250cc/min of N₂ had intermediate morphology between Photos 1-a and -b. The Ti or its nitride layer adhered tightly to the substrate.

The layers of Cr and its nitride showed similar morphology as regards flow rate of N₂. However, The Cr layer had finer unevenness than Ti one. When N₂ was introduced, the layer had coarser flakes than Ti nitride layers.

The crystal structures of the layers were examined by X-ray diffraction. The results are shown in Fig. 1-a and -b for Ti group layers and for Cr group layers, respectively. All layers for these profiles were plated at 400°C of the substrate temperature. As is shown, the crystal structure of the layer from Ti without N₂ consisted of, naturally, pure Ti metal. The layer with 50cc/min of N₂ was Ti₂N, and the layer with 250cc/min was TiN. In the case of the flow rate of Ar between 50 and 250cc/min, Ti₂N and TiN were simultaneously observed in one layer. Naturally, the ratio of TiN to Ti₂N became higher as increasing of N₂ flow rate.

The crystals in the plated layer had usually highly preferred orientation. Ti layer had a strongly orientated plane of (011) as shown in Fig. 1-a. Similarly Ti₂N had a plane of (002), and TiN had a plane of (111).

The crystal structure of a layer depends not only on changing the flow rate of N₂ but also on the temperature of the substrate. If the flow rate of N₂ was kept constant, the half height width of the profiles became sharper with increasing of the substrate temperature. However the crystal structure was not usually changed by the temperature of the substrate except at around a critical flow rate of N₂ (in this case, 100-125cc/min) where the ratio of TiN to Ti₂N in one layer changed drastically.

Similar phenomena, as regards ratio of CrN to Cr₂N and preferred orientation, were observed in the case of Cr and Cr nitrides, too. Cr₂N and CrN were simultaneously observed in one layer in a wide range of the flow rate between 100 and 300cc/min. The profiles became wider also when the substrate temperature decreased, especially when the flow rate of N₂ was as low as 50cc/min and the substrate temperature was 200°C. The Cr and its nitride layers did not adhere tightly than the Ti-group ones.

To investigate compatibility of a plated layer with its substrate, it is desirable to have only one type of crystal structure. Therefore, from above results, we adopted the conditions of (N_2 : 0, 50, 250cc/min) to obtain Ti and Ti nitride layers (Ti, Ti_2N , TiN), and conditions of (N_2 : 0, 100, 300cc/min) for Cr and its nitrides (Cr, Cr_2N , CrN). The substrate temperature was kept constant at 400°C.

When these samples were heat treated at 1000°C for 75 hours in a vacuum, some of them showed a drastic change. In the case of Ti on the pyrolytic carbon, the surface of the Ti became granular by the heat treatment. Cr layer on the pyrolytic carbon was separated from the substrate here and there. In the case of Ti- and Cr- nitrides on the pyrolytic carbon, rough honeycomb like cracks were found at all over the surface, although no photographs were shown here. The network of the cracks of Ti nitrides was 2-3 times coarser than one of Cr nitrides. It is possible that interaction between a reinforcement and matrix is caused at such cracks. Then coarser network is desirable. The cracks might be caused by the difference of thermal expansion coefficients between the layer and the substrate. To reduce the cracks, multiple plating of layers may be useful, if the thermal expansion coefficients can be changed gradually. The surfaces of Ti and Cr on the stainless steel lost their luster and became frosting. The Ti nitride layers (Ti_2N , TiN) on the stainless steel did not lose their golden luster. However, in the case of Cr nitrides on the stainless steel, scale was formed on the layer.

The morphology of the transverse sections are shown in Photos 2 to Photos 5, and the results of the composition analysis corresponding to each photograph are shown at right side of the photograph. The intensity of each element in the figure means approximately its weight fraction. Additional notes at right side of each photograph and at the top of composition analysis are as follows; a: protective coating or moulding plastic b: plated layer or reacted zone c: substrate The result of each combination of a layer and a matrix is described as follows:

Ti Layer on Pyrolytic Carbon

As shown in Photo 2-a and Fig. 2-a, carbon dissolved into Ti, and the carbon content at the Ti-C interface was approximately 0.19 and it decreased to 0.12 when the detecting position came closer to the surface of the Ti layer. This region of the carbon content corresponds to the nonstoichiometric region of TiC (7).

Ti_2N and TiN on Pyrolytic Carbon

The results of morphology and composition analysis after heat treatment were similar to each other except nitrogen content. Then only the results for TiN are shown in Photo 2-b and its corresponding figure. Although some cracks were found in the plated layer and slight dissolving of C into the layer was observed at the interface, the original composition of the layer was almost maintained.

Ti on Stainless Steel

Ti and Cr in the stainless steel diffused mutually in a wide range, and no Ti layer remained as shown in Photo 3-a and its corresponding figure. Even though Ti concentration had some peaks in the reacted zone, it decreased gradually as Fick's law when it came to inside of the stainless steel.

Ti_2N and TiN on Stainless Steel

Morphological change was hardly observed after the heat treatment. Original composition of the layer was almost maintained on the stainless steel, though small amount of Cr was detected on the layer as shown in Photo 3-b and its corresponding figure.

Cr, Cr_2N or CrN on Pyrolytic Carbon

The results of morphological change and composition analysis after heat treatment were similar to one another. All of the layers contained about 10wt%

of C at their interfaces and no nitrogen was detected around the layers as shown in Photos 4-a and -b and corresponding figures. The concentration of C in the Cr layer corresponds to a compound of Cr_7C_3 (9.00wt%C). The results for Cr_2N was exactly similar to one for CrN, so it was eliminated.

Cr on Stainless Steel

The Cr layer was lost from the surface similarly to the case of Ti layer. The plated Cr and some kinds of elements in the stainless steel diffused mutually. The results are shown in Photo 5-a and its corresponding figure. Concentration of Fe and Cr changed drastically at the interface between the diffused zone and the original stainless steel. The diffused zone contained about 30wt% of Cr which was miscibility limit of Cr in stainless steel, and Fe concentration was affected more than Ni by Cr concentration.

Cr_2N on Stainless Steel

Strange reaction was found as shown in Photo 5-b and corresponding figure. Though Cr_2N was maintained as the zone b', the layer of similar composition to stainless steel and the Cr rich layer at the surface were formed out side of the Cr_2N layer of b'.

CrN on Stainless Steel

Reaction was hardly observed, and the layer was maintained after heat treatment as shown in Photo 5-c and its corresponding figure. However many fine cracks are observed in the layer.

From these results, it is concluded as follows: Ti nitride layers adheres to carbon and also to stainless steel. Networks of the crack of Ti nitride layers are coarse. Ti nitrides react hardly to carbon and stainless steel. Therefore Ti nitride layer can be expected as an intermediate layer for a heat resisting material. In the case of Cr nitrides, the properties should be improved to use as an intermediate layer.

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Photo 2 Interaction of Ti and TiN with pyrolytic carbon
 a) Ti only b) TiN

Fig. 2 Composition analysis by EPMA
 Each figure corresponds to its left side photograph

Photo 3 Interaction of Ti and TiN with stainless steel
 a) Ti only b) TiN

Fig. 3 Composition analysis by EPMA
 Each figure corresponds to its left side photograph

Photo 4 Interaction of Cr and CrN with pyrolytic carbon
 a) Cr only b) CrN

Fig. 4 Composition analysis by EPMA
 Each figure corresponds to its left side photograph

Photo 5 Interaction of Cr, Cr₂N and CrN with stainless steel
 a) Cr only b) Cr₂N c) CrN

Fig. 5 Composition analysis by EPMA
 Each figure corresponds to its left side photograph